

Challenges and Opportunities in Cross-Sectoral Collaboration (CSC) in Bioeconomy

These results have been identified in ShapingBio analysis with the stakeholder groups of inetsors and companies and will be verified with policy makers and other stakeholder groups.

About

SHAPINGBIO

ShapingBio is an EU-funded project with the overall aim to support and accelerate bioeconomy innovation and the deployment of new knowledge in the EU and its member states.

ShapingBio aims to provide evidence-based and concrete information and recommendations for better policy alignment and stakeholder actions to realise the cross-sectoral potential of the bioeconomy and to reduce the fragmentation across biobased sectors and the food system, as well as in policies across regions, domains and governance levels.

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